

**THE FIRST IN THE CASE OF AN EMERGENCY EARTHQUAKE
FEATURES**

of medical care

Usmanov Kazbek Abdullaevich

Inspector of the Emergency Management Training

Center of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

usmanovkazbek23@gcom

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On April 26, 1966, an earthquake occurred in Tashkent almost on the site of an ancient fortress in the center of Tashkent. As a result of the earthquake, the central part of Tashkent was almost completely destroyed. More than 2 million square meters of living space, 236 administrative buildings, about 700 trade and catering facilities, 26 utilities, 181 educational institutions, 36 cultural institutions, 185 medical and 245 industrial buildings were destroyed. 78,000 families, or over 300,000 people out of the 1.5 million living in Tashkent at that time, were left without a roof over their heads. By decision of the government, instead of restoring the destroyed old one-story adobe houses, new modern multi-storey buildings were built in their place. The city was completely restored in 3.5 years [2].

One of the main reasons for the death of many people is natural disasters. Nowadays, it is impossible to predict when one or another natural disaster will occur, but it is possible to know the regions with a high risk. There are regions with a high risk of earthquakes and precipitation. Failure of large heat transmission networks, collectors, power plants, etc. as a result of earthquakes, as well as the occurrence of dangerous fires, also lead to severe burns and poisoning [1].

Earthquakes can cause more damage to urban and residential areas than to rural areas. The more industrial facilities there are in disaster areas, the higher the risk and the more complicated the situation. The injury that occurs during an earthquake depends on the speed, force, duration and location of the impact of the injurious agent and the age of the victim. Depending on the mechanism of injury, the following types of injuries are observed: shock, compression and mixed. Depending on the force of impact, a concussion can be of varying severity, from a concussion to a severe brain injury. Cases of unconsciousness and memory loss have been observed after injury. In the place of impact, soft tissue damage, various fractures can also be detected.

Under the influence of the compression mechanism (often observed with building and construction pieces and other equipment), the damaging force is not large. In rare cases, fractures and deformation of bones can be detected. In case of a mixed mechanism injury, musculoskeletal organs, skull, and brain tissue are injured, as well as crushing of body areas under the influence of load. Trauma to the skull and brain. Injury of the skull is characterized by a characteristic feature of the organism in the form of concussion-contusion syndrome. Trauma to the skull is accompanied by the formation of hematomas in soft tissues, disruption of their integrity (cracks), skull fractures, and brain injuries. Trauma to the skull can be open or closed. Anatomical integrity of soft tissues is not disturbed in case of closed injury of the head area. Due to damage to the subcutaneous vessels, a hematoma is formed and a swelling (bump) of different sizes appears in the head area. The affected area may experience pain, redness, and later bruising. In cases of open injuries, injuries appear due to the violation of the anatomical integrity of the tissues, and symptoms characteristic of injuries are observed [3].

In 8-15% of cases of skull damage, brain function disorders are noted. Closed injuries are 3 times more common than open injuries. When examining the injured person, it is important to determine the presence or absence of a skull

injury, the depth of the wound, and brain damage. Care should be taken to determine skin integrity, wounds, hematomas, or skull crush. Cranial aponeurosis wounds are usually more open than skin and subcutaneous tissue wounds. When determining the depth of the wound, attention is also paid to the nature of the secretions coming out of it. The amount of blood flowing from a wound can indicate whether or not the skull is damaged. Because when the bones of the skull are damaged, there is a lot of blood from the vessels and layers of the brain. The presence of cerebrospinal fluid or fragments of brain tissue during injury indicates that the injury has spread to the brain tissue. Eyelid swelling is a sign of an anterior skull base fracture, while bleeding from the ears indicates a medial skull base fracture.

There are three main types of brain injury in head injury: concussion, contusion and crushing. A concussion is caused by a quick and strong impact of a mechanical force. Depending on the clinical course, mild, moderate and severe degrees of concussion are distinguished. A mild concussion can cause short-term loss of consciousness, sometimes dizziness, ringing in the ears, blurred vision, headache, pale skin, nausea or vomiting. When injured, retrograde amnesia (forgetting the reality before the injury) is observed. At this severity of concussion, the above-mentioned symptoms gradually disappear after 5-7 days. In a moderate concussion, loss of consciousness, adynamia, mental agitation, vomiting, reduced reflexes, nystagmus, constriction of the pupil, slowing of the pulse, and acceleration of breathing are observed for several hours. A severe concussion is characterized by loss of consciousness for a long time (from several hours to days).

In this case, shallow breathing, slowness and weakness of the pulse, paleness of the skin, loss of reflexes, loss of reaction of the pupil to light, and involuntary excretion of urine and feces occur. All this can end in coma and death [3]. Concussion patients should only lie down. Up to three weeks for mild concussions, one to two months for more severe concussions. Brain damage. Cerebral palsy

refers to damage to the brain substance. In severe injuries, this damage is located on the opposite side of the impact of physical force. Cerebral palsy is also characterized by impaired brain function, and this condition develops suddenly after an injury. There is paralysis of the leg or arm (monoplegia) or the muscles of half the body (hemiplegia), loss of voice (aphasia), facial distortion due to damage to the facial nerves (asymmetry), and deterioration of vision. Body temperature can rise sharply up to 40⁰C.

The daily amount of urine increases, the amount of sugar in it increases. Complex treatment measures are used for 4–5 weeks. The main focus is on improving the functioning of the respiratory and vascular systems, and then on the elimination of neurological changes. Brain crush. A concussion occurs as a result of bleeding from veins inside the skull or broken bones. A collection of blood (hematoma) forms on the dura mater (epidural hematoma) and inside the brain tissue (intracerebral hematoma). The first symptoms of brain injury are: loss of consciousness, headache. Dilation of the pupil on the bleeding side is observed. Later, the patient's reaction to the external environment disappears, he faints, the pulse slows down to 40-50 beats per minute. Breathing becomes worse, noisy and uneven. As a result of bleeding in the brain, the signs of crushing appear after some time rather than immediately, so the injured should be under the strict supervision of doctors. Pre-medical care for skull and brain injuries consists of providing calmness to the injured, immobilizing the head area, improving breathing, that is, preventing life-threatening situations. Treatment of closed brain injuries should begin with creating absolute peace of mind for the patient. They should be transported lying down with their head slightly raised. Due to the fact that the patient is unconscious, measures are taken against the blockage of the vomit in the respiratory tract, the tongue falling out. It is necessary to bend the head to the side and put an air tube in the oral cavity. Sometimes it is necessary to give oxygen and cardiopulmonary resuscitation during transportation. A special board, stretcher or

stretcher with wheels is used for transporting a heavy patient. The stretcher with the patient is lifted without shaking with the help of two or four people [4].

When lifting the injured to the upper floors, it is necessary to remove the head to the front and the side of the leg to a horizontal position. When transferring the patient from the stretcher to the bed, the stretcher should be held at the level of the bed and 3 people should stand between the stretcher and the bed facing the patient. One person should hold the patient's head and chest, the second person should hold the waist and thigh, and the third person should hold the calf. Resilient construction of buildings, installation of fences and other special protective measures are of great importance in reducing the number of natural disasters.

The following measures should be taken to protect against earthquake damage inside the room: heating and other devices must be firmly fixed to the building wall, roof and roof coverings should be light, hard equipment should be fixed to the floor and walls, cabinets and refrigerators should be protected from shocks, televisions are a fire and explosion hazard.

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